

A new instrument to measure the global EoR signal

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Abstract

This engineering note evaluates a different approach for measuring the global EoR signal following in the footsteps of EDGES, LEDA and other such instruments. The key principle of this approach relies on a) the scalability of the antenna system, namely the antenna itself, the feed ports as well as the ground plane b) an exceptionally good match between the antenna and receiver system to reduce systematic uncertainty and c) an updated approach for measuring the antenna and receiver calibration parameters in the field without relaying at all on any laboratory characterisation. The advantage of this approach is to have a very well matched system comprised of several scaled antennas working over a wide bandwidth such as 3:1 or 4:1 and providing extra degrees of freedom to remove antenna beam chromatic effects which are otherwise difficult to calibrate out.

1 Introduction

The recent Nature paper by the EDGES team has made waves in the EoR community. However, what has now become apparent is that there are some issues which the authors have not fully addressed. One such issue is the lack of any beam modelling based on measurements which is extremely difficult to carry out in the field. It has been observed that the gain variation over frequency can easily result in an absorption feature at 78MHz. Even with beam measurements, it is debatable whether the accuracy required is ever achievable. In addition, parameters such as antenna efficiency are even more difficult to characterise to any reasonable accuracy in the field without changing the "antenna environment". The end result is that all of these antenna systematics which are not calibrated out sufficiently well get imprinted onto the measured signal. Questions have also been raised by Richard Hills and others about the validity of the foreground models used, in particular the fact that the parameters describing the foregrounds have nonphysical values.

Experiments such as EDGES and SARAS are susceptible to the same problems due to the fact that they are a single antenna experiment (or two identical antennas). LEDA tries to go further by using the large array to calibrate for the antenna gain but that too is fraught with difficulties.

The antenna used for these experiments has a fundamental requirement of spectral smoothness in both the antenna reflection coefficient and the gain. It is difficult to design a wideband antenna with greater than 2:1 bandwidth with such smoothness across the whole band and impossible to ensure an exceptionally good match to a reference impedance if the criteria is a reflection coefficient of better than say 17dB over such a wide bandwidth (less than 2% of the power is reflected back). If we examine the reflection coefficient of the EDGES antenna, it can be seen that they get close to this in the band where they claim to have made a detection.

It is my assertion here that actually a feasible approach which could potentially one day yield reliable results is one which attempts to decouple the antenna from the equation altogether. Of course this is not easy to achieve but with scalability and overlapping bands, there may be a chance. The reason being that with a truly scalable antenna, any residual which is a feature of the antenna chromaticity and has not been removed sufficiently well with calibration will potentially be present in some or all dipole signals and can thus in theory be removed once the data is patched together. This makes a big assumption about the sky (dominated by galactic synchrotron) being essentially spectrally smooth. The recent maps made by LWA1 at 9 frequencies from 35MHz to 80MHz show that this assumption may be realistic. Figure 1 shows the LWA1 spectral index map which is spectrally smooth with a clear flattening in the Galactic plane. Note that the authors explain that there are systematic artifacts in the north celestial pole and south galactic pole which show unusually steep or shallow spectrum, respectively.

2 The scalable antenna

The scalability concept is clearly not new. We have for years built scaled prototypes at frequencies which are convenient to measure and have generally been very successful at this. Even EDGES calls other band antennas termed "high" or "mid" as scaled versions and this is approximately true but does not meet the scaling requirement described here. For example the EDGES antennas have non scaled ground planes, antenna height and even general design not to mention they do not see the same band.

Figure 1: LWA1 spectral index map calculated over 35-80 MHz.

For this application, we want a simple "fat" dipole antenna design which scales linearly at different frequencies. The ideal bandwidth of the antenna is nearly 2:1, with the main design goal being to ensure match performance better than 17dB, which corresponds to a VSWR of 1.33 and only 2% reflected power. This is actually quite realistic meaning the antenna itself works over a wider range of frequencies (e.g 3:1) but is exceptionally well matched at a narrower range of frequencies. The reason why this is important is because the signal received by the antenna is partly reflected back from the terminals of the first amplifier (LNA) and then again from the antenna to re-enter the LNA with a different phase (described by Meys' formalism as noise waves). Reducing the average reflection of the antenna and LNA to a level of 1% may allow the experiment to be done with little calibration. The proposed calibration approach based on EDGES system is described later.

The overall model of a suitable dipole antenna is shown in Figure 2, where all the parameters are scalable including the box housing the electronic and calibration system and the metal ground plane (not shown). The antenna is called a planar "blade" dipole and is somewhat similar to the EDGES antenna. It is made of two fairly square blades which come together at the centre for a small transition to 50Ω . The nice feature of this antenna, whilst not being limited to dipole antennas, is that the design can be done without the need for a physical balun adding less uncertainty to the calibration. The EDGES system still relies on a balun which puts extra spectral structure onto the signal. It is difficult to calibrate the balun response sufficiently well. Raul Monsalve who has done much of the calibration for the experiment has also said that they would like to somehow get rid of the balun in their design.

The dipole arms can directly connect to the inner and the outer of the coaxial conductor and providing the gap is small, the output can be matched to 50Ω . At this transition there is a scalable but small (typically less than 8mm) PCB which converts the dipole output to coax. This transition board is essentially just a metal plate with an coaxial connector on the back and a short semi-rigid coax cable placed inside a scalable metal conduit to shield it from the antenna. The coax cable has to vary its length from antenna to antenna but this should have minimal impact if short. The antenna is mainly supported by the rigid metal box and support material such as Rohacell ($\epsilon_r \approx 1$) and the metal box is supported by a plastic structure underneath which is also scaled. This could in the first instance be made of PVC bars or sheets and a flat PVC base which is then fixed to the ground. The metal box can also be placed under the antenna ground plane.

In order to construct this antenna, the blades need to be cut from metal sheet and it should be noted that standard laser cutting achieves 10 micron accuracy. For our application we would only need mm accuracy. Based primarily on the aforementioned criteria (2% reflected power from the antenna) and a small feeding gap, EM simulations have been carried out (omitting the metal box underneath and the ground plane) to evaluate the response of the dipole with a design frequency of 44MHz as an example. Figure 3 shows the real and imaginary part of the antenna impedance as well as the 3D pattern. It is clear to see that the antenna impedance is very smooth and close to 50Ω between

Figure 2: One example of a scaled blade dipole antenna. The metal enclosure can also be placed underneath a metal ground plane.

32MHz to 60MHz. These points relate to the above-mentioned criteria. The pattern is also very smooth at the design frequency however we would look to repeat these simulations to take into account both the ground plane and the metal box plus any other supporting structure which will add ripples in the beam. Figure 4 then shows the current distribution for the antenna and particularly because of the small feeding gap, the current is mostly distributed near this gap and on the edges of the structure.

Figure 3: Blade dipole impedance and 3D pattern at 44MHz.

Choosing the number of dipoles to use in this experiment will almost entirely rely over what band the excellent match can be obtained and how much overlap is necessary to remove systematics. Once this first antenna is optimised, the others are just scaled versions of that. As an example Table 1 shows the possible scaling for 5 antennas to cover the band 30MHz to 130MHz. This table gives the dimensions of length (L), taper length (TL), width (W) and feed gap (FG) which is the size of the square transition PCB. Figure 5 shows the simulated return loss for these dipoles. The slight variation in the peaks and troughs is due to the surface mesh size in the EM simulator changing at different frequencies. For better accuracy this can also be fixed for the highest frequency antenna and used to calculate all other antenna responses. The important fact to note here is that the behaviour of these antennas will be very similar as well as the shape of the antenna beam including any sidelobes. The desire would be to increase the bandwidth of each antenna slightly and reduce the scaling factor so that they are separated by only a few MHz, enough to clearly distinguish "antenna" spectral features.

Figure 4: Blade dipole current distribution.

Table 1: Blade dipole scaling parameters using 5 antennas

Scale	FC (MHz)	L (mm)	TL (mm)	W (mm)	FG (mm x mm)
1.0	44	1,861	1,785	2,228	8 x 8
1.25	55	1,489	1,428	1,782	7 x 7
1.5	66	1,241	1,190	1,485	6 x 6
1.75	77	1,064	1,020	1,273	5 x 5
2.0	88	931	893	1,114	4 x 4

3 Calibration and readout system

In order to describe the calibration system proposed here, it helps to first explain the approach taken by EDGES. The EDGES in-situ calibration is carried out using effectively a three position switch, changing between an ambient 50Ω load (when noise source is off), a calibrated noise source and the terminals of the antenna connected to the input of the LNA circuitry. This can then be used to compute an "uncalibrated" antenna temperature, defined as

$$T_A^* = T_{NS} \frac{P_A - P_L}{P_{NS} - P_L} + T_L \quad (1)$$

where T_{NS} and T_L represent the best estimate of the noise temperatures produced by the noise source and load, respectively. Here P_A , P_L and P_{NS} represent the three power spectral density measurements of the antenna, load and noise source. To then calibrate this spectrum, a large number of laboratory measurements are required and the calibration data processing thus aims to establish a relationship between the uncalibrated antenna temperature, T_A^* , and the calibrated antenna temperature, T_A . This is done by replacing the power densities in equation 1 with models that rely on the noise wave parameters, given by

$$P_A = g[T_L(1 - |\Gamma_{rec}|^2) + T_0] \quad (2)$$

$$P_{NS} = g[(T_L + T_{NS})(1 - |\Gamma_{rec}|^2) + T_0] \quad (3)$$

Figure 5: Scaled blade dipole antenna with galvanic isolation.

$$P_A = g[T_A(1 - |\Gamma_{ant}|^2)|F|^2 + T_U|\Gamma_{ant}|^2|F|^2 + T_C|\Gamma_{ant}||F| \cos(\phi) + T_S|\Gamma_{ant}||F| \sin(\phi) + T_0] \quad (4)$$

given

$$F = \frac{\sqrt{1 - |\Gamma_{rec}|^2}}{1 - \Gamma_{ant}\Gamma_{rec}} \quad (5)$$

$$\phi = \arg(\Gamma_A F) \quad (6)$$

Here, g represents the system gain, T_A and T_0 are the calibrated antenna temperature and receiver noise temperature, and Γ_A and Γ_{rec} are the antenna and receiver system (input) reflection coefficients relative to 50Ω . The terms T_U , T_C and T_S are the uncorrelated and the correlated noise (sine and cosine terms) that reflect from the antenna terminals and re-enter the receiver with phase ϕ . This notation for the so-called "noise wave parameters" is largely defined in Meys[ref] and is due to the effective mismatch between the antenna and receiver. If there is a perfect match between the two (i.e. antenna and receiver reflection coefficient is 0), the noise wave parameters disappear from equation 4. By re-arranging these equations, we then have the primary equation to solve

$$T_A = \frac{1}{K_A}[C_1 T_A^* + (1 - C_1)T_L - T_U K_U - T_C K_C - T_S K_S - C_2] \quad (7)$$

were the K terms are the reflections between the antenna and LNA and are all determined by laboratory measurements of the receiver as it is connected to a particular calibrator (in our case this is all done in the field) and C_1 , C_2 , T_U , T_C and T_S are then all solved in the least squared sense once the measurements are at hand.

This system is characterised in the laboratory by a set of four calibrators, all of which are external to the LNA circuit. Measurements are carried out with a VNA and are then further modelled as low order polynomials and Fourier series. The data form a large system of equations (per calibrator and frequency channel) which when solved for provide the frequency-dependant calibration coefficients.

Whilst the aforementioned technique is extremely powerful, it is somewhat limited in the way that EDGES and any other instruments have implemented it. The main problem is that when you characterise an RF circuit in the laboratory at a certain temperature and then transport that circuit to a site and install it, then run the circuit for long periods of time with varying temperature, it can and most likely will deviate from the laboratory measurements.

In the second version of the EDGES experiment, this was remedied somewhat by having a VNA or impedance measurement circuit in the field, however this was only for measuring the antenna reflection coefficient not the LNA which is likely to cause the most spectral variation as a function of temperature.

The block diagram of the calibration system proposed here is shown in Figure 6 and is colour coded. Green is off-the-shelf components already housed in metal enclosures, orange are systems to develop and yellow are the systems we have already developed and are testing.

Figure 6: An updated calibration system relying on field measurements only to determine calibration coefficients. Green=COTS, orange=to develop, yellow=developed already

There are several important features which I will describe here. The dipole system is formed by the scaled antenna and the LNA calibration system. The system heavily relies on a number of mechanical switches which have exceptionally low loss (0.01dB) and a reported match better than 50dB. Whilst electronic switches are reliable, the most stable and low loss are electro-mechanical switches which have typically 90-110dB isolation between the ports. These are attached using very short high quality (low temp coeff.) semi-rigid cables.

The aforementioned switches facilitate the switching of both the independent standards for determining the calibration coefficients for our system as well as allowing the VNA to measure both the reflection coefficient of the antenna and the LNA. The VNA is small and portable and has a dynamic range of 135dB. It has two ports and is itself calibrated in the field using 3 standards (loads, an open and a short) per port and a through which connects one port to another.

For determining our calibration coefficients, the independent calibrators used are a 50Ω load, a 5dB ENR calibrated noise standard and a very accurate thermal noise standard which produces 380K Johnson noise. In addition to the external hot cold standard, two two long cable standards are used for the noise waves since these produce an impedance which rotates around the smith chart as a function of frequency. These are made with highly compact and flexible spaghetti size coax. Additional open and short standards are used for calibrating the input switch if needbe.

The receiver unit is designed with LNAs and several filters. The first and second LNA should also have an excellent match (and isolation) requirement for the reflection of the noise waves and this is easily achieved across a very wide band. The output is analogue fibre (via direct modulation) and is an area we have a great deal of expertise in. All of these components have been developed and tested over the years. Building an LNA module per antenna is quite straightforward as we have a great deal of experience in designing a range of receivers for several projects including amongst other, SKA and HERA.

The control signal transport is done primary by fibre to USB modules which are off the shelf and an Arduino which has a number of functions. It's main function is to switch the mechanical switches and measure temperature

with high accuracy. The only galvanic connection to each dipole system is a power cable (coax, SMA) which carried typically DC 36 to 48V.

The expectation is that the dipole systems are distributed around a field and connected via analogue fibre (e.g length 500m) to the processing system in an enclosure. The processing system is also shown in Figure 6. Here the signal is converted back to RF and connects to an FPGA board we had made which is based on a ROACH2 board housing two 14 bit dual input ADCs. The backend system has already been developed and is undergoing testing. To calibrate the ADC amplitude and phase for this digital readout system, a high power (band limited) calibrated noise source is used.

4 Site location and RFI

This scaled experiment will be just as susceptible to RFI as any other low frequency experiment. Therefore the proposed system can be built in a low RFI site such as the Karoo in South Africa or potentially a low RFI northern site such as Owens Valley in California since the effect of the galaxy coupling is reduced. A prototype system can be built at Lord's Bridge for demonstration. The expected cost to produce a prototype of the full dipole system including all the electronics and ground plane is approximately £15k to £20k.

5 Conclusions

This note has explored the potential of a simple scaled dipole system built for overlapping frequency coverage from 30-130MHz or beyond. The advantage of such a system over other single antenna global experiments is that scalability provides access to an exceptionally well matched wideband system and there is an extra degree of freedom with which to process the data and remove antenna systematics.

Most of the system described here can be developed with off the shelf components requiring only the antenna, LNA and housing to be developed. The antenna is developed using flat metal sheets which can be cut to much better accuracy than 1mm. Also the transition PCB can be made to the exact size per scaled antenna. The group has developed a great deal of expertise in producing scaled antenna systems over the past 10 years and this would no doubt help in the design of such a system.